

Convection in M-dwarf atmospheres

I. Grid of non-magnetic 3D hydrodynamical CO⁵BOLD model atmospheres

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ABSTRACT

Aims. In this study, the first in a series dedicated to the investigation of convection in the atmospheres of M-type dwarf stars, we present a new grid of non-magnetic 3D hydrodynamical model atmospheres, and study the influence of convection on the observable properties of non-magnetic M-type dwarfs.

Methods. The new grid of 3D hydrodynamical model atmospheres was computed with the CO⁵BOLD code and was supplemented with a grid of 1D hydrostatic models calculated with the LHD code. The two types of model atmospheres were computed using identical atmospheric parameters, opacities, and equation of state. This enabled us to directly compare their predictions and to assess the influence of convection on the atmospheric structures and observable properties of M-type dwarfs, such as photometric colors and the strengths of spectral lines.

Results. We found that the influence of convection had a limited impact on both the atmospheric structures and observable properties of M-type dwarfs at solar metallicities though the effects were slightly more pronounced in metal-poor dwarfs at $[M/H] = -2$. In particular, horizontal temperature inhomogeneities in the optically thin layers of metal-poor dwarfs were dominated not by radiation but by adiabatic cooling which the 1D hydrostatic models are not able to account for. We also found that the optically thick layers of the 1D models failed to replicate the thermodynamic structures of the 3D hydrodynamical model atmospheres, regardless of how convection was parametrized. While differences between the thermodynamic structures of the average 3D and 1D model atmospheres were negligible near the optical surface, radiative flux in the optical wavelengths was found to be extremely sensitive to TiO bands, which calls for extra care in modeling the formation of molecular lines in M-type dwarf atmospheres. Conversely, the photometric colors and spectroscopic lines at infrared wavelengths generally showed only limited sensitivity to convection.

Key words. Stars: atmospheres – Stars: low-mass – Convection – Hydrodynamics – Methods: numerical

1. Introduction

While M-dwarf stars are among the most numerous in the Galaxy, possibly comprising over 70 % of the stellar population (Henry et al. 2006), their low luminosity and severe contamination of their spectra with spectral lines make them less accessible targets for spectroscopic studies compared to hotter dwarfs and red giants. However, with the acceleration of exoplanet research, particularly due to new space-borne missions like TESS (Ricker et al. 2015) and PLATO (Rauer et al. 2024), red dwarfs have become increasingly studied as potential hosts for planets. This interest was driven by their high numbers relative to other stars and conditions favorable for harboring extraterrestrial life, such as low UV radiation, close habitable zones, and long lifetimes, with one in every six M-type dwarfs estimated to harbor a terrestrial planet within its habitable zone (Dressing & Charbonneau 2015).

Besides of interest in the context of exoplanetary research, cool M-dwarfs, which are expected to become fully convective and are among the most magnetically active cool stars, raise questions about the origins of stellar magnetism in the absence of a solar-like dynamo driving the process that have been explored in numerous studies (Li et al. 2024; Santos et al. 2019; Brun & Browning 2017; Newton et al. 2017; Reiners et al. 2012; West et al. 2004). At the same time, the processes occurring at the stellar surface are much less understood (Kochukhov 2021). Until now, the 3D hydrodynamical model atmospheres have been applied to study the role of convection in non-magnetic M-type dwarfs only in a handful of studies and have covered a limited range in effective temperatures, T_{eff} , gravities, $\log g$, and metallicities, $[M/H]$ (Ludwig et al. 2002, 2006; Wende et al. 2009; Wedemeyer 2013; Beeck et al. 2013). Therefore, the influence atmospheric parameters and metallic-

ity on convection in M-type dwarf atmospheres has not been investigated systematically yet and thus, is poorly known.

The contribution of the present paper is therefore two-fold: (a) we present a first extensive grid of 3D hydrodynamical CO⁵BOLD model atmospheres of M-type dwarf stars; and (b) by focusing on a small subset of models characterised by extreme values of T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[M/H]$, we investigate the influence of convection on the thermodynamic properties and velocity fields, as well as photometric colors and spectral line formation in non-magnetic atmospheres of M-type dwarfs.

2. Model atmospheres

2.1. 3D hydrodynamical model atmospheres

The new grid of 3D hydrodynamical model atmospheres of M-type dwarfs was computed with the CO⁵BOLD code, by employing box-in-a-star approach (Freytag et al. 2012). The grid covers the effective temperatures between 3000 and 4000 K with a step of 200 K¹, $\log g = 4.5$ and 5.0, and metallicities $[M/H]$ from +0.5, to -2.0 in steps of 0.5 (Fig. 1). This range in atmospheric parameters is characteristic to M-type dwarfs with spectral types from M0 to M5. The calculations employed MARCS opacities (Gustafsson et al. 2008), which were grouped into 14 opacity bins. The numerical resolution was set to $140 \times 140 \times 160$ points distributed equidistantly on the geometric scale and spanned optical depths from $\log \tau_{\text{Ross}} = +4.0$ to $-6 \dots -8$. All simulations covered at least 10 convective turnover times (measured by Brunt-Väisälä timescale). We used solar abundances from Asplund et al. (2005) and applied a constant enhancement of $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.4$ at $[M/H] = -1.0 \dots -2.0$ and $[\alpha/\text{Fe}] = +0.2$ at $[M/H] = -0.5$. To reduce the computational load, all further analysis of the 3D model atmospheres was using the 20 3D model structures computed at different instants in time (snapshots) and selected such that their properties would represent best those of the entire simulation run (see Dobrovolskas et al. 2013). Characteristic parameters of the model atmospheres are provided in Appendix A.

2.2. Average ⟨3D⟩ and 1D model atmospheres

To investigate the impact of convection on the internal structures and observable properties of M-type dwarfs, we also computed the average ⟨3D⟩ and 1D hydrostatic model atmospheres.

The average ⟨3D⟩ model atmospheres were obtained by computing the temporal and spatial average of the 3D structures in the 20 snapshot ensemble. Therefore, the ⟨3D⟩ model carries an imprint of convection on the average atmospheric structure. Obviously, the 1D models are free of such imprints although their structures are affected by convection via its parametrization using MLT (Kučinskis et al. 2018; Dobrovolskas et al. 2013).

The grid of 1D hydrostatic model atmospheres was computed with the LHD code (Caffau & Ludwig 2007), using the same atmospheric parameters (T_{eff} , $\log g$) and metallicities, as

¹ Actual model T_{eff} are within 50 K of targeted values. This is because T_{eff} is not an input parameter of a simulation, but controlled by the entropy of material flowing in through the bottom boundary.

Fig. 1. The grid of 3D hydrodynamical CO⁵BOLD model atmospheres of M-type dwarfs computed in this work (green filled rectangles). M-type dwarfs observed by the Kepler mission are shown for reference as black dots (Akeson et al. 2013). Earlier 3D hydrodynamical models of M-type dwarfs computed by other authors are shown for reference, too. Note that in this study the model atmospheres were computed at 6 different values of metallicity, while all previous models are of solar metallicity.

well as opacities and equation of state, EOS, as those used in the computation of the 3D hydrodynamical CO⁵BOLD model atmospheres. Therefore, differential comparison of the 3D and 1D model properties allowed us to assess the influence of convection on the atmospheric structures and observable properties of M-type dwarfs (see Sect. 3 and 4 below).

2.3. Selection of the mixing-length parameter for the computation of 1D LHD models

Convection in the LHD models is treated using mixing-length theory, MLT, as formulated by Mihalas (1978), where the mixing length parameter, α_{MLT} , has to be set beforehand. In the past, a number of authors have attempted to calibrate α_{MLT} so that the 1D models could be used to reproduce the internal structures of the 3D hydrodynamical models (see e.g. Ludwig et al. 1999; Trampedach et al. 2014; Magic et al. 2015; Sonoi et al. 2019).

Our tests with the models M-type dwarfs showed that precise fits to the average ⟨3D⟩ structures were very difficult to achieve with 1D hydrostatic model atmospheres. This was because the entropy profiles of the ⟨3D⟩ models show a knee-type upwards bend in the outer atmospheric layers (i.e. where convection “switches off”) and no choice of α_{MLT} in the LHD models allowed us to obtain satisfactory fits to the ⟨3D⟩ entropy profiles (Fig. 2). Similarly, fitting of the asymptotic entropy values at the inner atmospheric boundary did not yield satisfactory fits to the entropy profiles in the outer layers.

In those relatively few cases when it was possible to obtain reasonable least-squares fits, the determined α_{MLT} values were in the range of 1.7 and 2.1. Therefore, we adopted $\alpha_{\text{MLT}} = 2.0$

Fig. 2. Entropy profiles of the average $\langle 3D \rangle$ CO⁵BOLD models and the LHD models computed using different α_{MLT} values.

for the calculation of the LHD model grid. Luckily, the temperature profiles in the atmospheres of M-type dwarfs are only weakly sensitive to the choice of α_{MLT} , thus the resulting temperature profiles should be little affected by the exact choice of α_{MLT} .

3. Impact of convection on the atmospheric structures

One of clearly visible features of convective stellar atmospheres is the granulation pattern caused by the hot upflows and cool intergranular downflows. 3D hydrodynamic model atmospheres have successfully reproduced these patterns for the Sun and Betelgeuse (Nordlund et al. 2009; Freytag et al. 2002). As seen in Fig. 3, the M-dwarf models also exhibit granulation patterns, albeit at lower contrast, due to less vigorous convective upflows and downflows in the M-type dwarfs.

The granulation pattern in M-type dwarfs is solar-like, and the relative root mean square (RMS) wavelength-integrated intensity contrast decreases gradually towards the lower T_{eff} ,

Fig. 3. Examples of granulation patterns and horizontal temperature fluctuations in 3D hydrodynamical model atmospheres of different types of stars: the Sun (left); M0 dwarf: $T_{\text{eff}} = 4007$ K, $\log g = 4.5$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.0$ (middle); M5 dwarf: $T_{\text{eff}} = 3009$ K, $\log g = 5.0$, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = 0.0$ (right). The physical sizes of the model boxes are different: the Sun: $8 \times 8 \times 3$ Mm; M0 dwarf: $4 \times 4 \times 1$ Mm; M5 dwarf: $0.6 \times 0.6 \times 0.2$ Mm. Lower panels display vertical temperature cuts in the respective model atmospheres.

higher $\log g$, and lower $[\text{M}/\text{H}]$ (Fig. 4). The contrast serves as an effective indicator of convection intensity, as denser model atmospheres require less velocity to transfer the same amount of kinetic energy upwards.

This implies that the convective element is not displaced as rapidly and thus remains closer to thermodynamic equilibrium with the surrounding material (Fig. 5).

3.1. Thermal stratification

As long as radiative equilibrium dominates the heating and cooling past the convective layers, such as in solar metallicity M-type dwarf atmospheres, the differences between the average $\langle 3D \rangle$ and 1D temperature profiles remain small (Fig. 6). However, at lower metallicities, the influence of radiative heating and cooling diminishes, and adiabatic cooling driven by convective motions begins to affect the mean thermodynamic structure of the stellar atmosphere, potentially cooling the upper layers by several hundred K above $\log \tau_{\text{Ross}} = -2$. While

Fig. 4. Relative root mean square (RMS) wavelength-integrated vertical intensity contrast $\sqrt{\langle I^2 \rangle - \langle I \rangle^2} / \langle I \rangle$, and its dependence on the atmospheric parameters of M-type dwarfs.

Fig. 6. **Top:** $T - \tau$ relation of the average (3D) and 1D LHD models, characterized by different values of T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[M/H]$. **Bottom:** RMS horizontal temperature fluctuations from the average in the 3D hydrodynamical models.

Fig. 5. Relative RMS wavelength-integrated vertical intensity contrast versus the gas density at $\log \tau_{\text{Ross}} = 0.0$.

these layers do not contribute strongly to the continuum or atomic line formation, adiabatic cooling in the outer layers of M-type dwarfs may significantly influence the formation of molecular lines or the cores of strong lines.

4. Impact of convection on the observable properties

While M-type dwarfs are of low luminosity, they are the most numerous stars in the Galaxy and thus are commonly observed photometrically. Spectroscopic investigations of M-type dwarfs are more challenging because of their low luminosity, which requires long exposure times, and the complexity of their spectra, which makes the definition of continuum in the

observed spectra difficult even in the infrared (IR). However, given the recent interest in M-type dwarfs as potential planet hosts and thus, as interesting candidates for studies with the forthcoming spectroscopic surveys, such as 4MOST, WEAVE, accurate interpretation of their spectra becomes crucial, too.

4.1. Photometric properties

To estimate the influence of convection on the observable properties of M-type dwarfs, we computed spectral energy distributions (SEDs) and photometric magnitudes with the NLTE3D code (Steffen et al. 2015), using the same input data (such as binned opacities, EOS) as in the calculation of the 3D hydrodynamical CO⁵BOLD models and by utilizing the ATLAS9 (Castelli & Kurucz 2003) opacity distribution functions from Gustafsson et al. (2008). For this, we used the same procedures as outlined in Bonifacio et al. (2018) and Kučinskas et al. (2018). To compute the instrumental photometric magnitudes, we used the definitions of *UBVR_IJHK* filters from Kučinskas et al. (2018). In addition, we have computed photometric magnitudes in the KEPLER (Van Cleve & Caldwell 2009), TESS (Ricker et al. 2015), and PLATO (Rauer et al. 2024) filters.

The influence of convection was assessed by comparing the photometric magnitudes and color indices that were computed with the 3D hydrodynamical, average (3D), and 1D hydrostatic model atmospheres. With this, the 3D–(3D) differences measure the impact of horizontal inhomogeneities while the (3D)–1D difference show the impact on the photometric colors due to differences in the vertical temperature profiles of the (3D) and 1D models (see e.g. Kučinskas et al. 2013).

Several conclusions were apparent immediately from this analysis. Firstly, the influence of horizontal inhomogeneities on the photometric colors was negligible (Table 1). This was expected because temperature contrast in the M-type dwarf atmospheres is low (Sect. 3). Secondly, (3D)–1D differences were

very large in the visual range (V , R , Kepler, TESS, and PLATO filters). Inspection of the SEDs revealed that the largest differences were seen in the wavelength ranges where TiO molecular lines are located (Fig. 7). Again, this is expected given the extremely high sensitivity of the TiO opacities to temperature. However, close inspection of differences between the 1D and $\langle 3D \rangle$ temperature stratifications revealed that temperature differences in the continuum-forming depths were very small. This means that even very small differences in temperature stratification may lead to very different photometric magnitudes in filters that cover the TiO lines. Therefore, on the one hand, significant differences between the predictions of the 3D and 1D models may suggest that convection indeed plays an important role in the formation of TiO lines. On the other hand, extremely high temperature sensitivity of TiO opacities may mean that these differences could be caused by a variety of different effects, including those related to the numerical setup of the 3D hydrodynamical models and so forth. Therefore, this result suggests that molecular line formation in the M-type dwarf atmospheres should be treated with extreme caution both in the 3D hydrodynamical and 1D hydrostatic model atmospheres. This applies to solar metallicity M-type dwarfs whereas at low metallicities ($[M/H] = -2$) TiO lines are too weak to have a noticeable effect (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Ratios of 3D to 1D radiative fluxes for M0 and M5 dwarf model atmospheres.

4.2. Spectral line formation

To evaluate the influence of convection on the spectral line formation in the atmospheres of M-type dwarfs, we synthesized the profiles of several spectral lines that are prominent in the IR range of the M-type dwarf spectra, using for this purpose the 3D hydrodynamical CO⁵BOLD, average $\langle 3D \rangle$, and 1D hydrostatic LHD model atmospheres. Line profiles were

computed with the Linfor3D² code, under the assumption of local thermodynamic equilibrium, LTE, and using the same input data as in the computation of CO⁵BOLD models. We then calculated the 3D–1D abundance corrections that were defined as differences in the abundance of a given element obtained from the same observed line using two different types of model atmospheres (e.g. 3D–1D). For this, we have chosen a pair of relatively strong and weak lines for FeH (995.732 and 997.822 nm), K I (1177.2861 and 1177.6061 nm), Na I (1074.9393 and 1268.2639 nm), and OH (1518.3943 and 1687.1895 nm). Abundance corrections were calculated at extreme points of the M-type dwarf model grid in terms of T_{eff} , $\log g$, and $[Fe/H]$ (see model parameters in Table 1). To use appropriate microturbulence velocity values with the 1D models, we calculated individual microturbulence velocities for each spectral line using Method 1 described in Steffen et al. (2013) and found them to be of a few hundred m/s. For all analysed spectral lines, the 3D–1D abundance corrections were found to be below 0.01 dex, well below expected measurement uncertainty which indicates that the influence of convection on the spectral line formation in the M-type dwarf atmospheres is negligible.

5. Discussion

The influence of convection on the observable properties of M-type dwarfs was estimated using the models located at the extreme points in the M-type dwarf model atmosphere grid (see model parameters in Table 1). Our choice is justified by the fact that the properties of M-type dwarf atmospheres vary very slowly and smoothly with the atmospheric parameters. In all studies cases, we found that the influence of convection on the atmospheric structures and observable properties of M-type dwarfs is small.

We are confident that numerical resolutions of the model atmospheres chosen for this work are justified. Spatial resolution lower than the more widely used 240^3 is sufficient for computing models of M-type dwarfs. This is caused by the fact that horizontal inhomogeneities in their atmospheres are weakly expressed and therefore less computational effort is required to resolve them. However, if one is interested in significantly adiabatically cooled layers, higher resolution model atmospheres may be desirable to better resolve the propagation of waves. This is out of scope of this work, as the observable properties of M-type dwarfs investigated here form below the adiabatically cooled layers.

It is important to stress that M-type dwarfs are known to be among the most magnetically active main sequence stars, with mean magnetic field strengths reaching to 10 kG. We did not account for the magnetic fields when computing present model atmosphere grid because our main focus of study was convection in non-magnetic models. Key impact of magnetic fields would be further inhibition of convection, which at magnetic field strengths comparable to sunspots may significantly reduce the T_{eff} even if internal conditions of the star remained

² <https://www.aip.de/de/members/matthias-steffen/linfor3d-user-manual/>

Table 1. The 3D–1D magnitude corrections for several model atmospheres of M-type dwarfs. Indicated models correspond to those shown in Fig. 6 in order of the legend.

Filter	M0, [M/H] = 0		M0, [M/H] = -2		M5, [M/H] = 0		M5, [M/H] = -2	
	ΔM_{3D-1D}	$\Delta M_{3D-<3D>}$						
U	0.006	0.000	-0.008	0.000	-0.007	-0.002	-0.073	-0.003
B	0.003	0.000	-0.007	0.000	-0.054	-0.002	0.005	0.001
V	0.007	0.000	-0.008	0.000	-0.178	-0.001	0.038	0.003
R	0.003	0.001	0.017	0.000	-0.165	-0.001	0.069	0.004
I	0.000	0.001	0.006	0.000	-0.037	-0.001	-0.012	0.001
J	0.000	0.001	0.002	0.000	0.012	-0.001	-0.035	0.000
H	-0.005	0.000	-0.003	0.000	0.008	-0.001	-0.038	0.000
K	-0.003	-0.001	-0.008	0.000	0.008	0.000	-0.030	0.000
L	0.013	0.001	-0.008	0.000	0.013	0.000	0.001	0.000
KEPLER	0.006	-0.001	-0.010	0.000	-0.096	-0.001	0.035	0.002
TESS	-0.010	-0.004	-0.015	-0.001	-0.043	-0.001	0.005	0.001
PLATO	-0.033	-0.008	-0.021	-0.001	-0.076	-0.001	0.025	0.002

the same (namely entropy of the inflowing material). This may lead to degeneracy of T_{eff} and mean magnetic field strength of the model atmosphere.

While we have used LTE assumption for our spectral line synthesis calculations, we caution that accounting for the deviations from LTE (non-LTE or NLTE effects) has proven necessary for some species, such as K I lines (Olander et al. 2021). While we find the 3D effects to be of limited importance in the spectral line formation taking place in M-type dwarf atmospheres, it is crucial to recall that the 3D and NLTE effects are not additive and thus, full 3D NLTE analysis would be necessary to assess their combined effects.

6. Summary and conclusions

In this paper we presented the first extended grid of 3D hydrodynamical model atmospheres of M-type dwarfs, which spans the effective temperature range from $T_{\text{eff}} = 3000$ to 4000 K with a step of 200 K, $\log g = 4.5$ and 5.0, and metallicities from $[M/H] = +0.5$ to -2.0 with a step of 0.5 dex.

At solar metallicity, the influence of convection on the internal structures of M-type dwarf atmospheres is limited. However, adiabatic cooling – which is not accounted for in the 1D hydrostatic models – may alter significantly the $T - \tau$ profiles of the metal-poor M-dwarfs. Also, there is no choice of the mixing length parameter in the MLT parametrization of convection that would allow the 1D hydrostatic models reproduce the internal structures of M-dwarfs predicted by 3D hydrodynamical models in the optically thick layers.

Our analysis also shows that convection has minor effect on the photometric colors and strengths of spectral lines at infrared wavelengths. However, the picture is completely different in the optical wavelength range where, due to high sensitivity of TiO opacities to temperature fluctuations, the horizontal fluctuations in the strengths of TiO lines may become substantial. This calls for a particular care in modeling of molecule formation and dissociation in the atmospheres of M-type dwarfs.

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Appendix A: Properties of 3D hydrodynamic M-dwarf model atmospheres

Characteristic properties of the individual 3D hydrodynamical models in the M-type dwarf grid are provided in Table A.1. The contents of the Table are as follows:

- Columns 1–3: effective temperature, T_{eff} , surface gravity, $\log g$, and metallicity, $[M/H]$, respectively;
- Column 4: the relative RMS white-light vertical intensity contrast, defined as $\sqrt{\langle I^2 \rangle - \langle I \rangle^2} / \langle I \rangle$
- Column 5: entropy of the inflowing material at the lower boundary of the model box;
- Column 6: the mean gas density at $\tau_{\text{Ross}} = 1$;
- Column 7: the mean gas pressure at $\tau_{\text{Ross}} = 1$.

Table A.1. Various atmospheric parameters of the 3D model atmospheres.

T_{eff} [K]	$\log g$	[M/H]	I contrast	s_{inflow} [erg g ⁻¹ K ⁻¹]	$\log \langle \rho(\tau_{\text{Ross}} = 1) \rangle$	$\langle \log P_{\text{gas}}(\tau_{\text{Ross}} = 1) \rangle$
3977.5 ± 3.6	4.5	+0.5	0.05	1.18 × 10 ⁹	-5.86	5.32
4006.8 ± 2.2	4.5	0.0	0.05	1.05 × 10 ⁹	-5.45	5.70
3995.8 ± 1.8	4.5	-0.5	0.04	1.01 × 10 ⁹	-5.22	5.91
3999.5 ± 1.4	4.5	-1.0	0.03	9.70 × 10 ⁸	-5.00	6.12
4030.9 ± 0.9	4.5	-1.5	0.02	9.10 × 10 ⁸	-4.63	6.48
4024.0 ± 0.7	4.5	-2.0	0.02	8.60 × 10 ⁸	-4.30	6.79
3976.2 ± 2.2	5.0	+0.5	0.04	1.05 × 10 ⁹	-5.40	5.74
3982.6 ± 1.4	5.0	0.0	0.03	9.70 × 10 ⁸	-5.02	6.10
3979.1 ± 0.9	5.0	-0.5	0.02	9.40 × 10 ⁸	-4.80	6.32
4033.7 ± 0.9	5.0	-1.0	0.02	9.05 × 10 ⁸	-4.58	6.53
3989.6 ± 0.3	5.0	-1.5	0.01	8.55 × 10 ⁸	-4.22	6.87
3983.9 ± 0.2	5.0	-2.0	0.01	8.22 × 10 ⁸	-3.95	7.14
3787.2 ± 2.7	4.5	+0.5	0.04	1.28 × 10 ⁹	-5.95	5.30
3774.6 ± 1.3	4.5	0.0	0.03	1.17 × 10 ⁹	-5.63	5.60
3810.8 ± 1.2	4.5	-0.5	0.03	1.10 × 10 ⁹	-5.38	5.82
3818.8 ± 0.9	4.5	-1.0	0.02	1.05 × 10 ⁹	-5.17	6.01
3801.3 ± 0.4	4.5	-1.5	0.01	9.60 × 10 ⁸	-4.78	6.37
3769.5 ± 0.3	4.5	-2.0	0.01	9.10 × 10 ⁸	-4.49	6.64
3821.6 ± 1.8	5.0	+0.5	0.03	1.15 × 10 ⁹	-5.55	5.65
3811.0 ± 0.9	5.0	0.0	0.02	1.05 × 10 ⁹	-5.20	5.98
3842.7 ± 0.8	5.0	-0.5	0.02	1.02 × 10 ⁹	-4.99	6.19
3835.3 ± 0.4	5.0	-1.0	0.01	9.70 × 10 ⁸	-4.77	6.39
3828.9 ± 0.3	5.0	-1.5	0.01	9.05 × 10 ⁸	-4.41	6.73
3780.7 ± 0.2	5.0	-2.0	0.01	8.65 × 10 ⁸	-4.14	6.99
3591.8 ± 1.6	4.5	+0.5	0.03	1.40 × 10 ⁹	-6.03	5.31
3585.0 ± 0.9	4.5	0.0	0.02	1.28 × 10 ⁹	-5.74	5.56
3579.5 ± 1.0	4.5	-0.5	0.02	1.20 × 10 ⁹	-5.51	5.76
3593.4 ± 0.7	4.5	-1.0	0.01	1.15 × 10 ⁹	-5.33	5.92
3612.3 ± 0.3	4.5	-1.5	0.01	1.05 × 10 ⁹	-4.97	6.24
3595.7 ± 0.3	4.5	-2.0	0.01	9.70 × 10 ⁸	-4.65	6.53
3554.9 ± 1.6	5.0	+0.5	0.02	1.25 × 10 ⁹	-5.66	5.62
3615.6 ± 0.6	5.0	0.0	0.01	1.17 × 10 ⁹	-5.38	5.89
3616.8 ± 0.4	5.0	-0.5	0.01	1.10 × 10 ⁹	-5.14	6.10
3627.8 ± 0.3	5.0	-1.0	0.01	1.05 × 10 ⁹	-4.94	6.28
3621.7 ± 0.2	5.0	-1.5	0.01	9.50 × 10 ⁸	-4.54	6.63
3589.4 ± 0.2	5.0	-2.0	0.01	9.10 × 10 ⁸	-4.29	6.88
3428.7 ± 1.6	4.5	+0.5	0.03	1.45 × 10 ⁹	-6.09	5.30
3389.5 ± 0.9	4.5	0.0	0.02	1.37 × 10 ⁹	-5.83	5.53
3374.3 ± 0.6	4.5	-0.5	0.01	1.30 × 10 ⁹	-5.62	5.72
3395.2 ± 0.4	4.5	-1.0	0.01	1.25 × 10 ⁹	-5.46	5.87
3408.7 ± 0.3	4.5	-1.5	0.01	1.15 × 10 ⁹	-5.14	6.14
3381.6 ± 0.2	4.5	-2.0	0.01	1.06 × 10 ⁹	-4.84	6.41
3361.0 ± 0.6	5.0	+0.5	0.01	1.34 × 10 ⁹	-5.74	5.61
3417.6 ± 0.4	5.0	0.0	0.01	1.27 × 10 ⁹	-5.50	5.84
3411.2 ± 0.3	5.0	-0.5	0.01	1.20 × 10 ⁹	-5.27	6.04
3415.1 ± 0.2	5.0	-1.0	0.01	1.15 × 10 ⁹	-5.10	6.19
3367.2 ± 0.2	5.0	-1.5	0.01	1.05 × 10 ⁹	-4.76	6.49
3408.8 ± 0.2	5.0	-2.0	0.00	9.70 × 10 ⁸	-4.45	6.77
3166.5 ± 0.8	4.5	+0.5	0.02	1.49 × 10 ⁹	-6.16	5.26
3197.1 ± 0.4	4.5	0.0	0.01	1.43 × 10 ⁹	-5.93	5.48
3185.1 ± 0.4	4.5	-0.5	0.01	1.39 × 10 ⁹	-5.74	5.66
3193.0 ± 0.3	4.5	-1.0	0.01	1.35 × 10 ⁹	-5.59	5.80
3182.2 ± 0.2	4.5	-1.5	0.01	1.25 × 10 ⁹	-5.29	6.06
3196.2 ± 0.2	4.5	-2.0	0.01	1.15 × 10 ⁹	-5.00	6.31
3184.4 ± 0.4	5.0	+0.5	0.01	1.42 × 10 ⁹	-5.86	5.56
3188.7 ± 0.3	5.0	0.0	0.01	1.35 × 10 ⁹	-5.61	5.78
3230.3 ± 0.2	5.0	-0.5	0.01	1.30 × 10 ⁹	-5.41	5.97
3218.1 ± 0.2	5.0	-1.0	0.01	1.25 × 10 ⁹	-5.25	6.11
3218.7 ± 0.2	5.0	-1.5	0.01	1.15 × 10 ⁹	-4.94	6.38
3231.6 ± 0.1	5.0	-2.0	0.00	1.05 × 10 ⁹	-4.62	6.65
3009.1 ± 0.6	4.5	+0.5	0.02	1.52 × 10 ⁹	-6.24	5.21
2984.5 ± 0.4	4.5	0.0	0.01	1.48 × 10 ⁹	-6.04	5.41
2993.7 ± 0.4	4.5	-0.5	0.01	1.44 × 10 ⁹	-5.84	5.60
2998.5 ± 0.2	4.5	-1.0	0.01	1.41 × 10 ⁹	-5.70	5.73
3014.3 ± 0.2	4.5	-1.5	0.01	1.35 × 10 ⁹	-5.46	5.96
2981.1 ± 0.2	4.5	-2.0	0.00	1.28 × 10 ⁹	-5.22	6.17
3002.7 ± 0.4	5.0	+0.5	0.01	1.45 × 10 ⁹	-5.92	5.52
3009.4 ± 0.2	5.0	0.0	0.01	1.40 × 10 ⁹	-5.71	5.73
3021.1 ± 0.2	5.0	-0.5	0.01	1.35 × 10 ⁹	-5.50	5.92
3014.4 ± 0.2	5.0	-1.0	0.01	1.33 × 10 ⁹	-5.38	6.03
3003.0 ± 0.2	5.0	-1.5	0.00	1.23 × 10 ⁹	-5.08	6.30
3004.6 ± 0.1	5.0	-2.0	0.00	1.15 × 10 ⁹	-4.82	6.53